

Parliament of Ghana

The Clerk to the Committee
Committee on Constitutional,
Legal & Parliamentary Affairs
Osu-Accra

MEMORANDUM TO THE MEMBERS OF PARLIAMENT

SUBJECT: Response to request for written memoranda in respect to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021.

ISSUE

The passing of the above mentioned Bill would be an action against the human rights of Ghanaian citizens. It would risk the safety and security of those who identify as LGBTQ+ and their allies. There are also risks to the greater society and development of Ghana should the Bill pass.

BACKGROUND

Global Mamas is a registered NGO in Ghana. We directly employ over 80 Ghanaians, and provide sustainable livelihoods for an additional 300 Ghanaians; entrepreneurs and their employees. We are land owners and we are building Ghana's first fair trade and eco-friendly production facility, with the goal of employing up to 200 more Ghanaians in the coming years. Between 2016-2019 alone, we have paid our Ghanaian staff and partners almost GHS 6.4M which has been invested in children's education and their local communities. We are a Guaranteed Member of the World Fair Trade Organization and globally recognized for our work. We sell our fair trade products to tourists in Ghana in our two retail stores, as well as export our products around the world. We also host international volunteers and tourists to assist in and learn from our work.

As a fair trade organization, Global Mamas stands for human rights for all and are committed to non-discrimination. One of our founding principles that we commit to through our Guaranteed Membership in World Fair Trade Organization is *Principle Six - Commitment to Non Discrimination, Gender Equity and Women's Economic Empowerment, and Freedom of Association. The organisation does not discriminate in hiring, remuneration, access to training, promotion, termination or retirement based on race, caste, national origin, religion, disability, gender, sexual orientation, union membership, political affiliation, HIV/AIDS status or age.*

Thus we would like to take the opportunity of this invitation to submit a written memorandum to note that we stand firmly against the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021.

CONSIDERATIONS

Were this Bill to pass, it will put at risk the safety of Ghanaian citizens, our organization, our workers, and international volunteers. In fact, we would be forced to shut down our volunteer program and could no longer have our international employees visit Ghana, because we would not want to put any LGBTQ+ volunteers or staff in jeopardy by inviting them into Ghana with a threat of arrest, or worse. To date Global Mamas has hosted over a thousand volunteers, all of whom contribute economically throughout their lengthy stays in Ghana. With the halt to our volunteer program, a likely reduction in tourism, and the resulting impact to our local income, our ability to employ more women and build tourism in Ghana will be diminished, and the economic security of our organization will be endangered. And with a reduced demand for our products, Global Mamas may be forced to stop giving orders to the skilled craftswomen we partner with. It is likely that this Bill would also endanger our support from organizations such as the World Fair Trade Organization and our grantors, such as GIZ and USAID, who all strictly require the organizations they support to have and uphold anti-discrimination policies.

While we worry for the security of our community and organization, we would be remiss if we did not also address our concern for the economic development of Ghana as a whole. According to research conducted by USAID in 2014, “the analysis suggests that anti-discrimination laws covering sexual orientation have an especially strong correlation with GDP per capita.” It could be as much as, “\$1,400 more in per capita GDP”, per one additional right in the Global Index on Legal Recognition of Homosexual Orientation. We have attached the research should it interest you to read additional details related to the correlation of the rights of LGBTQ+ people and the development of Emerging Economies.

Ghana is such a wonderful country that puts tolerance at the center of its values. Ghana is an example to the world where Christians and Muslims can live together in harmony, tribal wars are a thing of the past, and visitors are welcomed with open arms. Ghana is seen to the world as the best African country to visit because of its peace, safety, and willingness to embrace and educate. This Bill goes against the core values of Ghana in so many ways and will do nothing more than harm its positive reputation and its citizens.

RECOMMENDATION

We strongly urge the Members of Parliament to take the health and safety of their constituents, as well as the economy of Ghana, under consideration and to vote against the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021.

- (1) Attachment: The Relationship between LGBT Inclusion and Economic Development: An Analysis of Emerging Economies